

THE ROLE OF DIGITAL DIPLOMACY AND YOUTH INITIATIVES IN FOSTERING INTERREGIONAL COOPERATION AND SUSTAINABLE PEACE WITHIN THE FRAMEWORK OF THE SCO.

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Abstract: *Established in 2001 with China, the Russian Federation, Kazakhstan, Kyrgyzstan, Tajikistan and Uzbekistan as members, the Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO) has remained one of the world's least-known and least-analysed multilateral groups. It makes little effort itself for transparency and is only patchily institutionalized in any case.¹ Such useful research materials as are available on it are often in Chinese or Russian.² Outside its participant countries, the SCO has attracted mainly sceptical and negative comment: some questioning whether it has anything more than symbolic substance, others criticizing the lack of democratic credentials of its members and questioning the legitimacy of their various policies.*

Key words: *Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO), Multilateral Organization, Obscurity, Understudied, Lack of Transparency, Weak Institutionalization, Limited Research, Skepticism, Criticism, Democratic, Credentials, Legitimacy, China, Russia, Central Asia*

Introduction:

“The Shanghai Cooperation Organization (SCO) started from solving boundary issues, grew from counter-terrorism cooperation, developed and deepened in political, economic, cultural, educational and other fields of cooperation, and gradually developed into a new model of multilateral cooperation. This paper intends to outline the main achievements, challenges and prospects of the SCO after the two decades of its existence. After debate and discussion, the results that emerge from this paper show that over the past 20 years since the SCO establishment in June 2001, its concept of cooperation has been constantly enriched and developed. Its cooperation mechanism has been constantly enriched and improved; and its areas of cooperation have been expanded. However, with its development over time and the advancement of its cooperation practices, the SCO also faces challenges and development difficulties on its way forward; these include the facts of: the intensification of great power game in the region, the weakness of the sense of community between its member states and the transformation of cooperation pattern faces after expansion. Looking ahead, the Shanghai Spirit will guide its multilateral cooperation vision. The SCO mechanism provides an important guarantee for its multilateral cooperation ahead. The new type of international relations will serve as an important driving force for its multilateral cooperation vision. Based on our findings, this paper reasoned that

the SCO is fully capable of exerting greater influence and delivering greater results in the years to come.”[3]

In my view, the Shanghai Cooperation Organization has played a significant role in maintaining regional security and stability, especially through its focus on counter-terrorism and border issues. Over time, it has also created a platform for economic and cultural cooperation among member states, which is important for strengthening mutual trust. However, I think the SCO still needs to overcome several challenges, particularly the lack of unity among members and the influence of great power rivalry in the region. If the organization can address these weaknesses and improve transparency, it will be able to enhance its role in global politics and become a more effective model of multilateral cooperation in the future.

Additionally SCO not only pays attention to only cooperation but also it considers interaction of innovation, cybersecurity, and digital education environment. It has been demonstrated that comprehensive digitalization of society is being accompanied by changes in the innovative potential and educational needs of Ukraine, especially in the development of the human intellectual capital and its protection in the digital environment. Human capital in innovation plays a significant role, especially in the digital age. Young people are considered as a vulnerable group that could be the main goal of cyber cognitive operations and as the weakest link of the System.[1]

Because of many criminals, literacy, people have difficulty making a living, even some of them have not enough money. Despite being such condition, each government tries to solving this kind of clues. Especially countries as SCO are eager to help them to get rid of uneducated condition

It is devoted to humanitarian cooperation within the framework of the SCO, that is, achievements, problems and perspectives. It analyses instruments and mechanisms of work in fields as such culture, education and public health service. The study reveals the main factors that restrain efficient cooperation in the humanitarian sphere, intercultural dialogue, and the development of common educational space.[2] I believe that humanitarian cooperation is one of the most important dimensions of the SCO’s activities because it directly affects people’s lives. The achievements in culture, education, and public health show that the organization is moving beyond security and economic interests, aiming to build stronger social ties among its members. However, I think the lack of deeper intercultural dialogue and the difficulties in creating a common educational space remain serious obstacles. If the SCO can strengthen mutual understanding between nations and invest more in

humanitarian projects, it will significantly increase the sense of community and long-term stability in the region.

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